

MODERN PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES ENSURING THE QUALITY OF TEACHING IN ENGLISH LESSONS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

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Annotation: Today, the focus is on the student, his personality, and his unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organizing students' educational activities that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of the use of new information technologies in secondary schools has been increasingly raised. These are not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the learning process.

Keywords: *psychological development, story-role-playing game, self-organization, intensive methodology*

Based on the peculiarities of the psychological development of younger schoolchildren, one of which is the predominance of the emotional sphere over the intellectual one, I chose game technology as the leading pedagogical technology in early English language teaching. In particular, as a leading educational activity – a story-role-playing game. In the story-role-playing game, the impressions of a junior schoolboy are constantly replenished, clarified, and qualitatively changed. The knowledge he has, thanks to their practically effective reproduction in the plot-role-playing game, becomes more durable, more conscious. Freedom, independence, self-organization and creativity of children in the story-role-playing game are manifested with special completeness. The creation of a unified system of scheduled and extracurricular work on the subject is the main task of the educational process. Only under the condition of an organic combination of regular and extracurricular work, a foreign language can make a significant contribution to the formation and development of a child's personality.

The initial training course is divided into three stages:

I. "Let's play English". Students in a playful way master the main types of speech activity - speaking, listening, get acquainted with the letters and sounds of the English alphabet, learn to read the first words.

II. "Let's read and write English". At this stage, all types of speech activity are being developed, but special attention is paid to reading and writing.

III. "Let's enjoy your English". At this stage, there is a further development of students' communicative competencies, as well as systematization and self-improvement of the acquired knowledge and skills.

In an effort to update the content and introduce new approaches in teaching a foreign language, focused on the development of pupils' communicative competence based on game technologies. Elements of intensive methodology, various forms of play activity, dramatization, dramatization contribute to the intensification of the learning process and ensure a high level of student learning. In my classes, I rely on the methods which, from my point of view, successfully combine all learning goals, take into account the psychological characteristics of children of early age. The program allows you to make learning understandable and joyful. The child learns by playing. To do this, interesting tasks are set for students in the course of training. The obvious advantage of this program is the presentation of lexical and grammatical material in a playful way, which is very important for children. Tired of serious educational material in other subjects, the school children easily and actively perceive problematic stories interesting to them in English lessons, plunge into the world of fairy tales. All this contributes to the emergence of a positive motivation for the subject English, and also encourages him to participate in activities in the classroom, at the same time develops the child himself. When school children have already mastered the basic skills of reading and writing in their native language, he has formed basic general educational skills, so he is ready for a more serious assimilation of more complex, not always corresponding to the equivalents of their native language, material in English. To combine programs, grades 2, 3, 4, I use such techniques and tools that allow me to build a lesson as an integral communication system: game situations like "fairy tales", interesting stories, the same actors familiar from other grades. The pupil must understand the meaning of everything that he has to reproduce, including grammatical constructions. Already from the first stage of learning English, I try to explain grammatical phenomena, but I do it with the help of game techniques, where dolls are also assistants. This is the formation of the plural of nouns, the negative structure with the verb can; the use of have (has, etc.). A young child loves to play very much, so one of the effective teaching methods is the use of various plots (for example, "Journey to the land of the Four Fairies", "Magic City"), stories (secrets, secrets of letters, the eternal adventures of Simon), game situations (the appearance of Karabas, Master Lomaster, Santa Claus). The main characters of my game plots in the lessons are dolls and toys. Dolls are my best assistants in English lessons: Alice, Simon, Pinocchio, Malvina, Dunno, etc. These

dolls are present from the first lessons, they talk about the countries of the language being studied, their families, friends, hobbies, teach children, enter into an argument with them, travel, arrange holidays. These dolls have their own biographies, a certain character, their own life stories. So, Alice and Simon are present at almost all lessons, Pinocchio sells us goods in the magic store, and is also a guide to school to Malvina. Malvina teaches us the letters and sounds of the English alphabet, tells us about her school. Dunno appears in those moments when we do not know something, we are experiencing difficulties, but together we find a way out of a difficult situation.

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